

A REVIEW ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF CEMENT CONCRETE THROUGH AGGREGATES AND CREATIVE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

An enormous number of concrete creation today gravely affects climate asset and energy. Hence this issue of substantial innovations affect the climate which is a basic issue in an unnatural weather change. The ongoing paper audits the substantial innovation and supportable advancement from past to future and researches reasonable concrete and material practice. Despite the fact that while contrasting these variables and the past, flow and future planned substantial manageability improvement, this exploration observed that the primary driver of an Earth-wide temperature boost is *CO2* discharge during cement and concrete creation. The arrangement of climate issue isn't to supplant the substantial by different substances and it can diminish how much concrete with cementitious materials. The best methodology for lessening how much *CO2* in conditions is utilizing Pozzolanic material and waste material, which the two assumes an essential part in the feasible substantial construction.

Keywords: temperature, concrete, material, development

INTRODUCTION

Strolling through urban communities without seeing cement in some form is unthinkable. Whether it is in the most recent skyscraper being developed, new side strolls being relieved, in streets associating the city, in dams, spans, marine designs, modern plants, and so on concrete is unpreventable. At the point when a material becomes as fundamental to the construction as concrete, it is vital to investigate its ecological effects on close on the off chance that the material is however feasible as it very well might be common. In the event that the material doesn't fulfill the certification of supportability it ought to be additionally grown, particularly in present society when earth unfavorable cycles are right now dependent upon examination. It is much of the time discussed whether cement would be able or ought to be viewed as a reasonable choice because of its specific properties and qualities. Concrete is made of a few unique components. In its most straightforward structure this incorporates concrete, water, and total. Concrete requires

significant measures of energy to deliver and delivers a lot of carbon dioxide. In any case, it can likewise be supplanted to a limited extent by valuable establishing materials. Concrete has a long help life; structures made of cement can generally be anticipated to last many years with legitimate support. Since the primary lifetime is so lengthy, possible waste on the off chance that one more kind of building material was utilized is decreased. Too, when a structure requires destruction, its material can be utilized for ensuing structures. Really, when a construction arrives at the finish of its valuable life, its substantial part can be totally reused into the totals to be utilized in other substantial combinations. Despite how much starting energy expected to create concrete, the material can possibly be proficient over its assessed future.

. A rundown of qualifications that should tended to while looking at the maintainability of a material is given:

1. Energy expected to create the material
 2. CO₂ emanations coming about because of the material's production
 3. Harmfulness of the material
 4. Transportation of the material during its assembling and conveyance
 5. Level of contamination coming about because of the material toward the finish of its valuable life
 6. Support required and the materials expected for upkeep
 7. Lifetime of the material and its true capacity for reuse on the off chance that the structure is destroyed
- It is essential to address these variables in choosing if a material can be seen entirely as a maintainable material. These elements can be isolated into two fundamental parts, typified energy is low, yet the functional energy is high then a material can't be considered supportable. An ideal arrangement would be a material with a low exemplified energy which brings about high functional energy investment funds. On the off chance that these two elements can be fulfilled then a material, when involved in light of supportability, is well headed to decreasing its ecological effect.

2.PROBLEM HIGHLIGHT

The issue was segment tension and innovation which is a biological system under extraordinary tension. To help individuals and make a superior condition for living and ventures substantially more proselyte unrefined substance to the purchaser that ought to be driving quicker . In modern movement is delivered climate contamination however it's anything but another issue. In Japan, North American, and Western Europe included 20% of the total populace . Albeit 80% complete energy P a ge | 2 on the planet and asset consuming due to exclusive requirement living likewise 5 billion individuals created has industrialization to following the best condition life . In light of Bueckert (1999) assessed the number of inhabitants on the planet that expanded 5 billion beginning around 1800 additionally in 1960 increment 3 billion individuals . Developing of populace request normal assets and development materials to fabricate framework like ports, water supply, house or sanctuary, disinfection, and transportation in light of standard life .

2.1PURPOSE OF ARTICLE

The ongoing paper is a survey on substantial innovation and feasible improvement from past to future and examination of reasonable concrete and material practice. In spite of the fact that contrasting these elements and past, current and future forthcoming substantial supportability advancement.

3.SUSTAINABILITY DEVELOPMENT

Sustainable development is a way to deal with development and human advancement that expects to address the issues of the present without compromising the capacity of people in the future to meet their own needs. The point is to have a general public where day to day environments and assets address human issues without subverting planetary integrity. Manageable improvement means to adjust the necessities of the economy, climate, and social prosperity. The Brundtland Report in 1987 assisted with spreading the word.

Supportable improvement covers with the possibility of manageability which is a standardizing concept. UNESCO planned a qualification between the two ideas as understands: "Maintainability is in many cases considered a drawn out objective (for example a more supportable world), while manageable improvement alludes to the many cycles and pathways to accomplish it." There are a few issues with the idea of economical turn of events. A few researchers say it is a confusing expression on the grounds that as indicated by them, improvement is intrinsically unreasonable. Different reporters are disheartened in the absence of progress that has been accomplished so far. A contributor to the issue is that improvement itself isn't predictably defined.

The Rio Cycle that started at the 1992 Earth Highest point in Rio de Janeiro has put the idea of supportable improvement on the worldwide plan. In 2015 the Unified Countries General Get together (UNGA) took on the Reasonable Improvement Objectives for the year 2030. These improvement objectives address the worldwide difficulties, including for instance destitution, environmental change, biodiversity misfortune, and harmony.

Fig.3.1 Sustainability development

3.1 Environment issue

Worldwide climate worry on an unnatural weather change, biodiversity, ozone layer, and resources exhaustion. Assets consumption and biodiversity are appearing in locally and provincially [8]. Anyway biodiversity is connected with the worldwide framework, and assets used on worldwide equilibrium, it is crucial for settle with them [9]. While these elements connect with P a ge | 3 the substantial businesses and development part. The result of development material and development activity straightly obliterated the climate and severely affect climate status. For example, the reasons for steel and concrete creation are enormous volumes of CO₂ outflow likewise development movement

spent a ton of petroleum product [9]. These elements effect on an Earth-wide temperature boost. Steel and concrete creation cause is expanding the enormous volumes of CO_2 outflow and development action utilizes a lot of non-renewable energy source. These exercises add to an Earth-wide temperature boost. As displayed in Figure 2 schematically the ecological issue groupings like worldwide, neighborhood, and constructed. The territorial climate would be happened air contamination, downpour, corrosive, and water contamination. During assembling the natural substance that pre-owned energy. These elements normally occurred and unsafe substances. It can recuperate these substances however depends to cost and innovation. The result of air contamination, downpour, corrosive, and water contamination is terrible effect on creation action in other locale. To explicit spot or city can be called nearby climate. The neighborhood conditions were happened soil contamination, land utilize west age, clamor, vibration, and dusty. These elements are being examined inside our regular routines. Soil contamination and west age connect with utilizing of cement. Land use too connect with development area [7-8]. To living and chipping away at climate is called assembled climate and it is encompassing. Building is structure to chipping away at the climate and living. "Albeit a subject to indoor contamination brought about by unstable natural mixtures (VOCs), parasites, and radiation" [9].

Environmental issues

3.2Economic issue

Climate issue shows in modern creation and offered various types of assistance which are plan to human existence. In the financial action would be utilized a ton of energy and assets [9]. In emerging nations currently have utilized countless energy and assets due to improve have the economy. In any case, emerging nations have lacking wares that have prompted creating useful movement and financial developing [10]. The monetary action can be given foundation. Specifically, this implies development of the street, building, rail lines, burrows air terminals, ports, extensions, dams, and different designs as displayed in Figure 3 which lead financial movement in every country.

Fig.3.2.1 Economic survey infrastructure

3.2.1 Effect of concrete on economy

The aggregate sum of substantial cast consistently "on the planet is like a mountain with an area of 1×1 km, and a level equivalent to that of Mt and this volume is over two times that of the wide range of various structure materials together additionally over the last 10 to 15 years the middle for the utilization of cement has moved from Europe and North America to Asia" [11]. As of late China is the biggest shopper of cement and maker of cement on the planet. China is utilizing more than "a big part of the concrete on the planet, or two times as much as Europe and the US together and Concrete was involved 4.3 billion tones in 2014 on the planet" [12]. In Figure 4 shown the worldwide concrete creations have expanded in most modern nations. Concrete creation is considerably more supporter of ozone harming substance outflows. Accordingly substantial industry considerably influences the environment of our planet. In 2008, "India passed the US as the second biggest creation and utilization nation of concrete and in 2010, India had a utilization of 216 billion tons, as most would consider to be normal to develop to 425 billion tons in 2020 and 860 billion tons in 2030" [11]. Kulkarni (2011) uncovered the India Gross domestic product was created 9% in 2001 and 2010 in light of substantial utilization as displayed in Figure 5 [13]. In 1900 concrete utilization was 10 million tons, in 1948 concrete utilization was 100 million tons, in 1968 concrete origination was 0.5 billion tons and 1989 concrete utilization was 1 billion tons in around the world. The expense of concrete and cement are unique in relation to one country to one more nation as displayed run of the mill normal costs in Figure 6. In 2011, the expense of per ton concrete in the US was 110 USD and cost of cement per m cubic was 130 USD [14]. In 2011, the expense of per ton concrete in the China was 53 USD and cost of cement per m cubic was 65 USD [15]. In 2011, the expense of per ton concrete in Norway was 146 USD and cost of cement per m cubic was 163 USD [15].

3.3 Social issues

Entire human exercises incorporate a particular social part or the like. The financial and natural issue incorporates a major number of social action. Unfortunate social frameworks are leading to ecological issues that transform into social issues [9]. "Agricultural nations, whose monetary development is an outright need, should be effectively engaged with framework advancement. Creating frameworks gives a premise to monetary extension, and yet, it has significantly expanded the natural effect of financial turn of events and our definitive objective is to have a serene world with equivalent circulation of riches, from a solid worldwide climate" [9].

4. Sustainability in concrete technology

The concrete is most boundless material and utilized broadly in development on the planet. Concrete is thoroughness and give infrastructural and straightforwardly run financial advancement and soundness of it, additionally need personal satisfaction [14]. Cement can be delicately coordinated and manufactured in entire classification of any structures and underlying framework in the building site or elsewhere. It is test to plan anyplace that is the upside of cement than other development materials. In Figure 8 shown three significant component can be support structure arrangement of substantial innovation and maintainability improvement.

Fig.4.1 Sustainability in concrete technology

5.PROTECTION OF CONCRETE MAKING MATERIALS IN OVER A SIGNIFICANT TIME SPAN

Enhancements in the substantial and concrete enterprises concerning manageability can be accomplished when moves are made by all gatherings required to utilize present day progressions like supplanting of concrete with Pozzolanic materials or waste materials and these can be appropriately consolidated in power plants and the metallurgic business [15]. Concrete is the significant piece of development material and broadly utilized on it. The significant piece of cement is three principal fixings which a Portland concrete, total, water, and admixtures in view of explicit execution measures of cement. Beginning around 1989 substantial industry was created 560 million tons of coal debris yet there are involved just 25 million tons as Pozzolanic materials and absolutely 5% is accessible Fly debris [10]. At present, creation of coal debris is 650 million tons. Albeit the ongoing creation of fly debris is 450 million tons that it's generally reasonable for utilizing as Pozzolanic. On the planet consistently spend a great deal of fly debris by substantial industry and the pace of fly debris utilization in each year is 30 million tons, likewise other Pozzolanic material creation, for example, iron impact heater slag and generally reasonable for substantial industry. Slag creation 100 million tons/year [13]. The application worth of concrete substitution is still low, subsequently in numerous nations can't be created manageable admixture like slag, etc. Slag is handling into the granulated or cementitious structure. Mehta (1997) assessed the size of coal debris and iron impact Furnace slag happened and accessible on those nations that would be request enormous greatness concrete in the future [15]. (For example 200 million tons of coal debris in very year delivered by China and India together and 250 million tons/year created coal debris by European nations, chiefly Russia, Poland, previous Czechoslovakia, Romania, Germany, Spain, and the Assembled). India, China, and Europe nations creation 100 million tons/year of impact heater slag. To track down a way to utilize all coal debris and Iron impact heater slag, either in state of blended Portland concrete or as a mineral admixture in concrete. It ought to satisfy those undertaking to need concrete without increment the current limit Portland concrete clinker creation [15]. Concrete and substantial ventures attempt to work on his economical turn of events and a fine way for the arrangement of the issue. Around 90% of slags and coal cinders are delivering today, the two of them have low worth of utilization, for example, involving in landfill and asphalt or basic arranged.

6.STURDINESS APPROACH OF SUBSTANTIAL MAINTAINABILITY

The majority of the businesses creating the fly debris, silica smoke and slag were supplanted into the concrete and decreases how much CO_2 outflow and progress the properties of new and solidified substantial states [16, 17]. "aside from upgrading the rheological properties and controlling draining of new concrete, these materials enormously work on the solidness of cement through control of high

warm slopes, pore refinement, consumption of concrete soluble bases, protection from chloride and sulfates entrance and proceeded microstructural improvement through long haul hydration and Pozzolanic responses albeit cement can give, through substance restricting, a place of refuge for the majority of the harmful components present in modern squanders; and there are solid signs that these mineral admixtures can likewise diminish the seriousness of substantial toughness issues emerging from Deferred Ettringite Development and Thaumasite" [18].

7.COMPREHENSIVE METHODOLOGY PLAN FOR MANAGEABILITY ADVANCEMENT OF CEMENT

The improvement of Substantial materials for strength, and sythesis SF, slag, FA or other various sorts of pozzolans materials as pivotal and essential constituents of the substantial creations are the principal issues and a central key development towards achieving sensible improvement of the Concrete and Substantial Industry [18]. Consequently, it ought to be "sassy and wry of us to accept that maintainable advancement in the development business can be accomplished just by using siliceous modern side-effects in concrete alone" [19]. It is fundamental to comprehend the substantial trademark, for example, all encompassing plan the materials to have great strong substantial designs. This technique would consolidate the going with.

New structure of concrete

Plan of new substantial construction must strong and ecologically:

Portland Concrete should not be utilized alone in concrete □ The substantial should be planning with reuse material; FA, SF, LW, etc.

Creation of concrete materials for Sturdiness and not so much for STRENGTH. Configuration substantial construction for manageability improvement: P a ge | 8

Plan to limit the site squander

Design concrete structure for sustainability development

Squander material decrease and waste material removal

Imaginative plan, A nearer examination of setup loads: Stay away from over-plan

Legitimize obliteration

8.POZZOLANIC MATERIAL TYPES FOR CONCRETE MANAGEABLE TURN OF EVENTS

1)Fly Debris or Crushed Fuel Debris

It is created from red hot pummeled (finely ground) coal to control electric age. The sythesis of these are "shales and muds (items in silica, alumina and iron oxide) and different items in coal, liquefy while in suspension, and afterward with fast cooling, they are done by the pipe gases and structure into fine circular particles" [20]. The Fly Debris particles are generally roundabout alive and well and reach in size from 0.5 µm to 100 µm. Fly debris is significant Pozzolanic material that it enjoys different benefits and assessed with conventional Portland concrete. Fly Debris has a decent lower intensity of hydration that it has made well known cementitious materials for a mass substantial design. Past explores have researched the use of fly debris as added substance substantial gives positive results similarly as mechanical and creation properties [21, 22].

2)Silica Smoke

SF is item from "silicon and ferrosilicon combinations from high immaculateness quartz and coal in a lowered curve electric heater which it has a powder with particles having measurements multiple times less than those of anhydrous Portland concrete particles and the main impacts in the utilization of silica raga as an admixture in concrete based materials are expansions in elasticity, compressive strength, compressive modulus, flexural modulus, and the malleable flexibility, yet diminishes in the compressive pliability, it upgrades the freeze-defrost toughness, the vibration damping limit, the scraped spot obstruction, the bond strength with steel rebar, the substance assault opposition likewise the erosion opposition of building up steel" [20]. Expansion, SF can be diminished the soluble base silica response, porousness, the drying shrinkage, coefficient of warm development, creep rate, and dielectric steady. [21, 22].

Ground Granulated Impact heater Slag

It is is gained by stifling fluid "iron slag (delivered by iron and steel particles) from a shoot heater in water or steam, to make a shiny, granular thing that is then dried and ground into a fine powder likewise use of slag or slag concrete regularly upgrades usefulness and decreases the water demand as a result of the extension in stick volume brought about by the lower relative thickness of slag" [20].

Rice Husk Debris

Almost to 600 million tons of rice paddy are delivered consistently all over the planet. "On mean, 20% of RHD is created, with a yearly creation of 120 million tons and rice husk is an external front of rice, that is delivered (almost 90% by mass) during de-husking of paddy rice additionally the Rice is affluent in silica content, obtained by consuming rice husk to remove flighty normal carbon, for instance, cellulose and lignin in spite of the fact that it is assessed RHA, one ton of rice yields 200kg of husk and around 40kg of powder" [20]. In view of Mehta, the undefined silica powders with the high surface domain are more responsive than the translucent kind of silica. The fineness of debris will impact the reactivity of RHD in the lime, mortar [20, 21, 22, and 23].

5)Met kaolin (MK)

Met kaolin is "refined kaolin dirt that is terminated (calcite) under painstakingly controlled conditions to make a formless alumina silicate that is responsive in cement and supplanting Portland concrete with 8% - 20% (by weight) met kaolin delivers a substantial blend which shows great designing properties, including: the filler impact, the speed increase of OPC hydration, and the Pozzolan response" [20].

8.1Pozzolan materials advantage for concrete sustainability

As of late development enterprises generally involved Pozzolan materials in the substantial construction likewise for soil adjustment because of their specialized strength, climate cordial, and financial reasons [21, 22]. Valuable cementitious materials are including GGBFS, FA, SF, RHA, MK, and POFA, to give some examples. The utilization of Beneficial cementitious materials in substantial design can for the most part lessen how much concrete and diminish *CO2* emanation from the climate, which, accordingly, can diminish development costs, give material providers, project workers, and specialists with significant benefits [23]. In addition, despite the issue in concrete paired yet the sythesis of cementitious beneficial can provoke various central focuses, for instance, improved substantial strength, sturdiness of cement, functionality of cement, etc [24].

9.REUSED AGGREGATE TYPES FOR CONCRETE SUSTAINABILITY

Modern waste a material has been utilized in the substantial creation is a gone through which could be gone back of not many periods. Brito (2015) assessed "The wide measure of concrete blends shaped with fly debris. Silica seethe and granulated impact heater slag and silica rage, which are all losses from modern and the at the ongoing time, applications had been as yet standing made to acquire new materials that could be appropriated in substantial creation, and thusly give more feasible development producers" [25].

9.1Crushed marble recycled aggregate

Martins et al. (2014) and André et al. (2014) considered the mechanical and toughness related act and do, separately, substantial blends in with reusing coarse total finished acquired as of industry of marble [26, 27]. The scientist made look at between the exhibitions of this "substantial blend with straight blends of blends made with limestone totals, basalt, and quartzite albeit compressive strength had been deficiency of 10% that was caused full substitution of coarse NA, in contrast with the substantial combinations, with the exemption for modulus of flexibility and struggle to scraped spot(28% will misfortunes up and 51% separately), ordinarily, the rundown of reused total as of squashed marble just impacted a slight decrease in all properties" [25]. The analyst assessed the mechanical and toughness act and complete, exclusively, coincidentally, the presence of the better part of the marbles in squashed [28, 29]. The outcome result uncovered compressive strength misfortune guideline esteem between range 10 and 20 percent.

9.2Recycled aggregates ground rubber tyres

The analyst thought about on strength and mechanical and - connected act and execution, exclusively, of blends concrete underlying to make by reusing ground elastic from utilized tires. [30, 31]. "Concrete blended in with the ground elastic from utilized old tires and framed substantial blends through unused level 5, 10, and 15% with ground elastic tires, with divergent sizes and shapes and the utilization of reusing tires total has been gotten through the strategy of cryogenic" [25]. The retention of 15% percent of this material impacted compressive strength misfortune values between range 46 and 52% percent Figure 8 the substantial compressive strength by expanding RA from oversaw elastic tires. The utilization of reused total from tires ground elastic in the substantial production impacted a significant decrease in the sturdiness complete [30]. Then again, it is available that the presence of this materials allowed delivering substantial blends by means of a similar water focus in with capillarity rates to these of the substantial alluded in Figure 9 shown the water retention elastic tires by expanding The scientist considered the way of behaving of blends mix concrete, ready with reused ground elastic total of utilized tires, when presence presented to fire and the outcomes had been so clear [32, 33]. This material has been enormously exposed to the greatness of reused elastic total, and higher substitution levels impacted a more unfortunate warm.

9.3Glass recycled aggregates

The analyst assessed the solidness and mechanical properties of concrete and blended west glass in with concrete [34, 35]. This west material can be diminishing compressive strength around 20 % while the utilization of reused glass total essentially get going a 10% lessening for the comparative substitution level of 20% percent by then the level of this decline expanded. This west glass has been allowed delivering substantial mix blends and affected on financial of cement [31, 35].

9.4Recycled aggregates from plastic waste

Babafemi (2018) evaluated “utilization of recycled waste plastics in concrete as a partial aggregate replacement has a clear effect on the properties of the material also this material is to be used in concrete in large quantities, it is important to know the relationship between the addition of recycled waste plastics and the engineering properties and in most cases, waste plastics have been used in concrete either as fine or coarse aggregate although utilization of this type of waste in concrete is beneficial from an environmental point of view, it's engineering (e.g., mechanical and thermal) properties are essentially different from natural aggregates” [36].

10.MOVE TOWARD OF CEMENT SUSTAINABLE BUILDING AND ADMINISTRATION

Isaia and Gastaldini (2004) report that in their items it consumes 5.5GJ of energy and deliveries generally 1ton of *CO2* per ton of clinker [39]. Japan has likewise gained an extensive variety of substantial industry innovations to limit expected impact and focus on *CO2* outflow control and reusing [40]. Those conclusions assisted with decreasing *CO2* emanations from assembling of concrete; unit-based *CO2* in Japan. Taking into account that 1ton of concrete has around 70% of clinker, it is seen that a year are given by the concrete business, around 1 billion tons of *CO2* into the air. In spite of the numbers are not agent face worldwide *CO2* outflows (addressing on normal 6% of the all out gave, obviously can't be neglected), concrete assembling for use in concrete had been reshaped to screen practical worldwide turn of events. There are essentially two different ways of diminishing how much *CO2* in the climate brought about by concrete creation: Lessening creation amount (limit creation), and Substitution of the "unadulterated concrete" at least one mineral admixtures, generally modern side-effects normal instance of fly debris and impact heater slag, turning the item environmentally right concretes [36, 37, 38].

11.CONCLUSION

Sustainability assumes an imperative part in financial improvement both universally and locally. Because of the enhancements in substantial manageability that is fundamental to comprehend the effect of many issues in the substantial plan stage, development stage and life pattern of the substantial construction, for example, "strength" and the main issue is saving the asset and energy in the environment. This study has summed up the assessment of substantial innovation and economical improvement from past to future and found the primary driver of an unnatural weather change which is *CO2* discharge during the development of cement and concrete. Likewise this study tracked down the best methodology for lessening how much *CO2* in conditions is Pozzolanic material and west material both as assuming a crucial part in feasible substantial construction. Albeit this study checked on the idea of economical advancement in substantial enterprises which is utilizing how much cementitious and Pozzolanic material rather OPC because of the protection of substantial substances, solidness plan of the substantial construction, and comprehensive methodology plan for the substantial parts. These are three significant mainstays of reasonable turn of events. Albeit this study assessed what's in store possibilities of substantial innovation and manageability advancement, as of late the vast majority of worldwide associations are dealing with substantial supportability improvement to diminish how much *CO2* outflow by half until 2050. These associations proposed four stages for diminishing how much *CO2* outflow in light of the concrete ventures and substantial creations in all around the world which is the establishment of new innovation in old and new concrete plant in view of warm and electric exhibitions, The petroleum derivative should be subbed of synthetic and regular

oil due to less CO_2 , escalated and more fills (waste) and biomass energizes, clinker replacement, and Carbon catch and capacity.

REFERENCES

- [1] Weaver P, Jansen L, Van Grootveld G, Van Spiegel E, Vergragt P. Sustainable technology development. Routledge; 2017 Sep 8.
- [2] Mulder KF. Strategic competences for concrete action towards sustainability: An oxymoron? Engineering education for a sustainable future. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev.* 2016 Mar 25:1-6.
- [3] Bjork, F. "Concrete Technology and Sustainable Development." CANMET/ACI International Symposium on Concrete Technology for Sustainable Development. 1999.
- [4] Cheung, M., and S. Foo. "Technology Real Property Services Branch Public Works and Government Services Canada." Use of Fly Ash in Concrete: proposed PWGSC Guidelines, CAN MEET International Symposium on Concrete Technology for Sustainable Development. 1999.
- [5] Bueckert, D., Canadian Press AThe World Braces for 6 Billion@, Vancouver Sun, September 24, 1999.
- [6] Juenger MC. sustainable Low CO_2 cement concrete. *Routledge Handbook of Sustainable and Resilient Infrastructure.* 2018 Dec 17:377.
- [7] Gjorv O, Sakai K. Concrete technology for a sustainable development in the 21st century. CRC Press; 2014 Apr 21.
- [8] Sim, Jongsung, Minkwan Ju, and Kihong Lee. "Thirty Years Researches on Development for Sustainable Concrete Technology." In MATEC Web of Conferences, vol. 138, p. 03008. EDP Sciences, 2017.
- [9] Sakai K, Noguchi T. The sustainable use of concrete. CRC press; 2012 Jul 26.
- [10] Swamy RN. Designing concrete and concrete structures for sustainable development. In Sustainable Development of the Cement and Concrete Industry. Proceedings of CANMET/ACI International Symposium, Ottawa, Canada 1998 Oct 21 (pp. 245-255). [11]Jahren P, Sui T. Concrete and sustainability. CRC Press; 2013 Jul 16.
- [12] Jonsung S, Lee KH. Sustainable Concrete Technology. *Civil Engineering Dimension.* 2015 Dec 18; 17(3):15865.
- [13] Kulkarni V.R. Concrete Sustainability: Current Status in India and Crucial Issues for the Future. Presented at Concrete Sustainability through Innovative Materials and Techniques, Roving National Seminars, Bangalore, and January 10–14, 2011.
- [14] Mehta, P.K, AAdvancements in Concrete Technology@, Concrete International, June 1999, pp.69-76. P a ge | 13
- [15] Mehta, P.K., "Bringing the Concrete Industry into a New Era of Sustainable Development," Proceedings of the Mario Collepardi Symposium on Advances in Concrete Technology, pp. 49–68, 1997.
- [16] Malhotra VM, Mehta PK. Pozzolanic and Cementitious Materials, Gordon and Breach Publishers, SA, 1996, 191 pp. Coarse aggregate.;1225(1225):1225.
- [17] Swamy RN. Design for durability and strength through the use of fly ash and slag in concrete. Special Publication. 1997 Aug 1; 171:1-72.

- [18] Al-Mana AB, Haneef M, Maslehuddin M. Effect of cement replacement, content, and type on the durability performance of fly ash concrete in the Middle East. *Cement, Concrete and Aggregates*. 1986 Jan 1; 8(2):86-96.
- [19] Swamy RN. Designing concrete and concrete structures for sustainable development. In *Sustainable Development of the Cement and Concrete Industry*. Proceedings of CANMET/ACI International Symposium, Ottawa, Canada 1998 Oct 21 (pp. 245-255).
- [20] Mukherjee SP, Vesmawala G. Literature review on technical aspect of sustainable concrete. *International Journal of Engineering Science Invention*. 2013 Aug; 2(8):1-9.
- [21] Altwair NM, Kabir S. Green concrete structures by replacing cement with pozzolanic materials to reduce greenhouse gas emissions for sustainable environment. In *Proceedings of 6th International Engineering and Construction Conference (IECC'6)*, Cairo, Egypt 2010 Jun 28 (pp. 28-30).
- [22] Meyer C. The greening of the concrete industry. *Cement and concrete composites*. 2009 Sep 1; 31(8):601-5.
- [23] Ismail MS, Waliuddin AM. Effect of rice husk ash on high strength concrete. *Construction and building materials*. 1996 Oct 1; 10(7):521-6.
- [24] Owaid HM, Hamid RB, Taha MR. A review of sustainable supplementary cementitious materials as an alternative to all-Portland cement mortar and concrete. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*. 2012 Sep; 6(9):287-303.
- [25] Brito J, Silva R. Use of waste materials in the production of concrete. In *Key Engineering Materials 2015 (Vol. 634, pp. 85-96)*. Trans Tech Publications.
- [26] Martins P, Brito JD, Rosa A, Pedro D. Mechanical performance of concrete with incorporation of coarse waste from the marble industry. *Materials Research*. 2014 Oct; 17(5):1093-101.
- [27] André A, de Brito J, Rosa A, Pedro D. Durability performance of concrete incorporating coarse aggregates from marble industry waste. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2014 Feb 15; 65:389-96.
- [28] D. Silva, F. Gameiro, J. de Brito, Mechanical properties of structural concrete containing fine aggregates from waste generated by the marble quarrying industry, *J. Mater. Civ. Eng.* dx.doi.org/10.61/ (ASCE) MT.1943, (2014).
- [29] Gameiro F, De Brito J, da Silva DC. Durability performance of structural concrete containing fine aggregates from waste generated by marble quarrying industry. *Engineering Structures*. 2014 Feb 1; 59:654-62.
- [30] Valadares F, Bravo M, de Brito J. Concrete with used tire rubber aggregates: Mechanical performance. *ACI Materials Journal-American Concrete Institute*. 2012 May 1; 109(3):283.
- [31] Bravo M, de Brito J. Concrete made with used tyre aggregate: durability-related performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2012 Apr 1; 25:42-50.
- [32] Correia JR, Marques AM, Pereira CM, De Brito J. Fire reaction properties of concrete made with recycled rubber aggregate. *Fire and Materials*. 2012 Mar; 36(2):139-52.
- [33] Marques AM, Correia JR, De Brito J. Post-fire residual mechanical properties of concrete made with recycled rubber aggregate. *Fire Safety Journal*. 2013 May 1; 58:49-57. [34] Serpa D, de Brito J, Pontes J. Concrete made with recycled glass aggregates: Mechanical performance. *ACI Mater. J.* [accepted for publication]. 2015 Jan 1.

- [35] de Castro S, de Brito J. Evaluation of the durability of concrete made with crushed glass aggregates. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2013 Feb 1; 41:7-14.
- [36] Babafemi A, Šavija B, Paul S, Anggraini V. Engineering Properties of Concrete with Waste Recycled Plastic: A Review. *Sustainability*. 2018 Oct 25; 10(11):3875.
- [37] Sakai K. Sustainability in fib Model Code 2010 and its future perspective. *Structural Concrete*. 2013 Dec; 14(4):301-8.
- [38] Sobotka T, Skirbekk V, Philipov D. Economic recession and fertility in the developed world. *Population and development review*. 2011 Jun; 37(2):267-306.
- [39] Henry M, Kato Y. Perspectives on sustainable practice and materials in the Japanese concrete industry. *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*. 2011 Sep 16; 24(3):275-88. [40] Isaia G, Gastaldini A. Concreto “verde” com teores muito elevados de adições minerais: um estudo de sustentabilidade. In *Conferência Latino-Americana de Construção Sustentável X Encontro Nacional de Tecnologia do Ambiente construído*, São Paulo, SP. Anais... CD-ROM 2004 Jul.
- [41] Khokhar MI, Rozière E, Turcry P, Grondin F, Loukili A. Mix design of concrete with high content of mineral additions: Optimisation to improve early age strength. *Cement and Concrete Composites*. 2010 May 1; 32(5):37785.
- [42] Joseph P, Tretsiakova-McNally S. Sustainable non-metallic building materials. *Sustainability*. 2010 Feb